

Comparison Of Effectiveness Of Piroxicam With Aceclofenac +Paracetamol In The Treatment Of Osteoarthritis

M. Mani Ratna¹, B. Keerthika¹, T. Guru Lahari¹, A. Sneha², K. Thirumala Naik²

¹PharmD Intern, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupathi, Andhra Pradesh, India.

ABSTRACT

A prospective observational study was done to investigate the comparison of effectiveness of piroxicam (50 subjects, 20mg twice in a day) with aceclofenac and paracetamol (50 subjects, 325+100 mg twice in a day) on osteoarthritis of knee subjects. The assessment tools for the pain intensity includes VAS (visual analogue scale) and for joint stiffness and physical function includes WOMAC (western Ontario and Mc master universities osteoarthritis index). The treatment period of 6 months conducted on 100 subjects diagnosed with knee osteoarthritis were divided into two groups. Group A received Aceclofenac and paracetamol (50 subjects) and group B received piroxicam (50 subjects). Subjects included both the male and female with age group of 45-60 years at baseline and after follow up treatment. Data were analysed by using student t test with significance of $p < 0.05$. Each group shows significant improvement in VAS and WOMAC. The aceclofenac shows greater reduction in pain intensity and improvement in physical function. Gastrointestinal, hypersensitivity side effects were shown in piroxicam.

Keywords: Osteoarthritis, progressive, degenerative, difficulty in moving knee joint, degradation of cartilage, physical examination, x-ray, Non-Steroid Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDS), platelet-rich plasma, physical therapy, joint replacement.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis is a multifactorial, progressive, enlightened, non-inflammatory degenerative disorder of synovial disease and cartilage. Osteoarthritis is the most common form of arthritis and mostly acts on one or several di arterio-dial joints, including large joints (such as the knee and hip joints) and small joints (such as hands) which is a leading cause of chronic disability among old age people^{1,2&3}. In OA, cartilage loss, osteophyte formation (bone spurs), and subchondral bone sclerosis leads to pain, disability, and a reduction in quality-of-life⁴.

Knee Osteoarthritis most commonly affects the knee in the body. It affects the bones, the synovial and the cartilage in the knee joint, it develops when the

cartilage of the knee wears off which leads to an overgrowth of the bone underneath. The cartilage becomes rough and breaks down, mainly resulting in swelling, difficulty in moving knee joint, and getting pain in knee⁵.

Hip Osteoarthritis is the second most common localization of osteoarthritis. The hip osteoarthritis is usually linked to the femoroacetabular morphology, with abnormal articular shearing and tearing forces resulting in a chronic inflammation process. Also, a proinflammatory state due to homeostatic imbalance led to cartilage degradation⁷. OA shoulder is the consequence of destruction of the articular surface of the humeral head and glenoid and which results in pain and loss of function⁶.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Figure :1 Osteoarthritis Of The Joints

Prevalence of OA is increasing because of the rising elderly of the population in developed and developing countries as well as rise in risk factors leading to OA³. Women are more likely to be affected than men⁹. Osteoarthritis is the second most common rheumatologic problem and it is the most frequent joint disease with a frequency of 22.1% to 39.0% in India. Nearly, 45% of women over the age of 65 years have symptoms of OA. OA was estimated to be the 10th leading cause of nonfatal burden¹⁰. Primary Osteoarthritis (idiopathic or non-traumatic): the result of articular cartilage degeneration due to without any

reason like age, genetic predisposition, obesity, gender. Secondary Osteoarthritis (traumatic or mechanical misalignment): the result of articular cartilage degeneration due to known reason like Joint Injury or Overuse, Muscle Weakness, Other Diseases like Rheumatoid arthritis, Infectious arthritis, Gout, Hyperparathyroidism, Haemophilia, Hypertthyroidism, Sickle cell disease, Avascular necrosis^{14,15,16}. These factors cause cartilage repair and lead to joint space narrowing, pain and stiffness⁵.

Figure :2 Risk Factors For Osteoarthritis

Osteoarthritis progresses through 4 stages. **Stage 0** is considered pre-osteoarthritis and describes a normal, healthy joint before the disease manifests. **Stage 1 (minor)**, there is minimal cartilage damage and possible formation of bone spurs. **Stage 2 (mild)**

includes more cartilage wear and narrowing of space with mild pain and stiffness. **Stage 3 (moderate)** includes cartilage erosion, inflammation and increase pain and stiffness. **Stage 4 (severe)** characterized by significant cartilage loss, chronic pain and joint deformity^{6,7}.

Figure :3 Stages Of Osteoarthritis

Osteoarthritis symptoms commonly present with the point pain indicates inflammation and degradation of cartilage. joint stiffness especially in morning or after period of inactivity. Other signs include swelling, tenderness and cracking sound during joint movement. Joint deformity and muscle weakness around the affected joint⁸. Physical examination is important in making the diagnosis. Confirmation is supported by x-rays which shows joint space narrowing, bone spur formation and osteophyte formation. MRI may be used for early cartilage assessment⁹.

Treatment goals for osteoarthritis are to minimize both pain and functional loss, Comprehensive management of the disease involves both non-pharmacologic and pharmacologic therapies. Pharmacological management aims to reduce pain and inflammation. first line drugs include for mild pain paracetamol, for moderate and severe pain NSAIDs are prescribed (Eg: aceclofenac, paracetamol, piroxicam). Topical NSAIDs are used to treat localized treatment. Intra articular corticosteroids help in short term pain relief for swelling and pain. Hyaluronic acid is a high molecular weight polysaccharide, and is a major component of synovial fluid and cartilage. Platelet-rich plasma injections may also improve osteoarthritis symptoms, used to improve joint function. Glucosamine sulphate is a nutrient supplement, used to relieve musculoskeletal symptoms. Non pharmacological management includes health education to promote positive and optimistic attitudes towards the disease, regular low impact exercise, weight loss, and physical therapy to improve joint strength and flexibility. use of walking aids to reduce joint strain. life style

modifications are essential for long term management.

Surgery includes joint replacement or arthroscopy is recommended when conservative treatment fails and pain and disability is severe^{10,11}.

DRUG PROFILE:

PIROXICAM:

MECHANISM OF ACTION: The mechanism of action of piroxicam, like that of other NSAIDs, is not completely understood but involves inhibition of cyclooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2). Piroxicam is a potent inhibitor of prostaglandin (PG) synthesis in vitro. Piroxicam concentrations reached during therapy have produced in vivo effects. Prostaglandins sensitize afferent nerves and potentiate the action of bradykinin in inducing pain in animal models. Prostaglandins are mediators of inflammation. Because piroxicam is an inhibitor of prostaglandin synthesis, its mode of action may be due to a decrease of prostaglandins in peripheral tissues.

Indications and Usage:

Piroxicam capsules are a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug indicated for

- Relief of the signs and symptoms of osteoarthritis
- Relief of the signs and symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis

Dosage and Administration:

- Use the lowest effective dosage for shortest duration consistent with individual patient treatment goals
- OA: 20 mg once daily

Adverse Reactions/Side Effects:

Most common adverse reaction are:

Nausea	Headache
Constipation	Edema
Abdominal pain	Dizziness
Diarrhoea	Rash

Contraindications:

- Known hypersensitivity to piroxicam or any components of the drug product
- History of asthma, urticaria, or other allergic-type reactions after taking aspirin or other NSAIDs

Warnings and Precautions:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hepatotoxicity • Hypertension • Heart Failure and Edema • Renal Toxicity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatal Toxicity • Hematologic Toxicity • Serious Skin Reactions • Anaphylactic Reactions
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Drug Interactions:

- Drugs that Interfere with Haemostasis (e.g. warfarin, aspirin, selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors [SSRIs]/serotonin norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors [SNRIs])
- Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE) Inhibitors, Angiotensin Receptor Blockers (ARB), or Beta-Blockers
- ACE Inhibitors and ARBs
- Diuretics
- Digoxin^{12&13}

ACECLOFENAC:

MECHANISM OF ACTION: Aceclofenac belongs to a group of medicines called nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). These drugs have anti-inflammatory and painkiller properties. It works by blocking the production of hormone-like substances called prostaglandins. Prostaglandins are released at the sites of injury, tissue damage and immune reactions. Prostaglandins play an important role in both the inflammatory response of the body and stimulating the reabsorption of bone in diseases.

Indications and Usage:

Aceclofenac is used to relieve pain and inflammation in patients suffering from:

- Arthritis of the joints (osteoarthritis). This commonly occurs in patients over the age of 50 and causes the loss of the cartilage and bone tissue next to the joint.
- Autoimmune disease that causes chronic inflammation of the joints (rheumatoid arthritis).
- Arthritis of the spine which can lead to the fusion of the vertebrae (ankylosing spondylitis).

Dosage and Administration:

- **For adults:** The usual dose is 100 mg twice daily (one tablet in the morning and one in the evening).
- **For elderly patients:** The same 100 mg twice daily dose is often prescribed, but dosage adjustments may be necessary based on overall health and kidney function.

Adverse Reactions/Side Effects:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inflammation or irritation of the lining of the stomach (gastritis) • Dizziness • Constipation • Nausea (feeling sick) • Diarrhoea 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased liver enzymes in the blood • Vomiting • Mouth ulcers • Itching • Rash • Inflammation of the skin (dermatitis)
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Contraindications:

Aceclofenac is strictly contraindicated in the following situation:

- Hypersensitivity to any component of drug
- Patient with asthma or a history of asthma triggered by aspirin or other NSAID'S.

Warnings and Precautions:

- GIT (gastrointestinal tract) bleeding, stomach ulceration, or perforation as NSAIDs
- Hepatic (liver) or renal (kidney) problems.
- Crohn's disease (chronic inflammatory bowel disease)
- Heart, liver, or kidney disease
- Blood clotting problems
- Systemic lupus erythematosus
- During pregnancy
- Lactation.

Drug Interactions:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antihypertensive Drugs • Diuretics • Cardiac Glycosides Like Digoxin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corticosteroids • Anti-Coagulants¹⁴.
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PARACETAMOL:

MECHANISM OF ACTION: Paracetamol is a weak inhibitor of PG synthesis of COX-1 and COX-2 in broken cell systems, but, by contrast, therapeutic concentrations of paracetamol inhibit PG synthesis in intact cells in vitro when the levels of the substrate arachidonic acid are low (less than about 5 μ mol/L). When the levels of arachidonic acid are low, PGs are synthesized largely by COX-2 in cells that contain both COX-1 and COX-2. Thus, the apparent

selectivity of paracetamol may be due to inhibition of COX-2-dependent pathways that are proceeding at low rates.

Indications and Usage:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headache • Tension headache • Migraine • Backache • Rheumatic and muscle pain • Mild arthritis/osteoarthritis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toothache • Period pain (dysmenorrhoea) • Colds and flu symptoms • Sore throat • Sinus pain • Post-operative pain • Fever (pyrexia)
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Dosage and Administration: 325mg twice a day

Adverse Reactions/Side Effects:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allergic reactions, which may be severe and include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Skin rashes, itching or hives ○ Swelling of the throat, tongue or face ○ Shortness of breath or wheezing • Loss of appetite and Yellowing of the eyes and skin can occur. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skin rash or peeling, or mouth ulcers • Breathing problems • Unexplained bruising or bleeding • Liver problems • Nausea • Sudden weight loss
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Contraindications:

- Contraindicated in known hypersensitivity to paracetamol in hepatic failure.
- Contraindicated in known hypersensitivity to paracetamol in renal failure.
- Pregnancy and breastfeeding.

Warnings and Precautions:

- Liver diseases

- Kidney disorder
- Myasthenia Gravis
- Low levels of potassium in the blood.

Drug Interactions:

- Medications to help relieve nausea (metoclopramide or domperidone)
- Medications to treat high cholesterol (cholestyramine)
- Medications to treat epilepsy (lamotrigine)
- Medications to treat tuberculosis (isoniazid)
- Medication to treat fever or mild pain (aspirin, salicylamide)
- Barbiturate and tricyclic antidepressants to treat depression (amitriptyline)
- A medication to treat gout called probenecid
- A medication used to treat bacterial infections called chloramphenicol.
- A medication used in HIV infections and AIDS called zidovudine¹⁵.

METHODOLOGY:

A prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 6 months spanning from December 2024 to May 2025. In the Department of Orthopaedics at Sri Balaji Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Renigunta, Tirupati

STUDY CRITERIA:**INCLUSION CRITERIA:**

- Individuals aged 50 to 65 years.
- Individuals who are willing to engaged in the study and attend follow-up appointments.
- Patients with Grade 2,3,4 (Kellgren Lawrence)

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patients with Rheumatoid arthritis or inflammatory bowel disease.
- Patients exhibiting hypersensitivity to medication.

STUDY MATERIAL:

- Patient informed consent form (Annexure I)
- Patient form data collection proforma (Annexure II)
- Western Ontario Mc Master university index (Annexure III)
- Visual analogues scale (Annexure IV)
- Kellgren Lawrence (Annexure V)

METHOD OF STUDY:

Baseline clinical and demographic characteristics will be obtained from the [inclusion criteria] patients. Data will be collected using a Proforma. Data collection includes patient information. Data collection regarding Prescribed Medication if any

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Statistical analysis is done by WINDOWS 11.VAS and WOMAC score in our study between two groups were compared using student t test (T-TEST). Standard deviation and mean of VAS and WOMAC score between two groups before after treatment are calculated.

The results of study were explained in the form of tables, bar, diagrams, and pie charts. Mean and standard deviation value of various parameters were calculated. Standard deviation, P value of VAS and WOMAC score of before and after treatment were calculated using students t test.

RESULTS:

Prospective observational comparative study was conducted for 6 months from DEC 2024 to MAY 2025 in orthopaedic unit in SRI BALAJI MEDICAL

COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH INSTITUTE, Renigunta, and Tirupati.

A Total of 100 knee OA subjects were categorised into two groups i.e. Group-A (50 subjects Treated with Combination of Aceclofenac + Paracetamol & GROUP-B (50 Subjects Treated with only Piroxicam) on their type of therapy. Out of 100 patients 59 were females and 41 were males. explain of gender in two groups from the study sample. We categorised the Subjects to their age groups. The average age of the total study population is 55 and the average age of the Aceclofenac + Paracetamol and Piroxicam is found to be 55 and 55 respectively.

Out of 100 subjects 29 subjects (29%) of them were from a group 45-50 years followed by 25 (25%) from 61-65 years, 23 (23%) from both 51-55, 56-60 years of subjects. explain about the distribution of subjects in two groups respective of their age. We have assessed the occupation status of the study subjects and percentage of Teachers & Bank Employees is found to be 7% followed by Agriculture Formers (32%), Daily Labourer (15%), Tailoring work (5%), Software (5%), Business (2%) and Home Makers (30%) which is explained in the We have assessed the risk factors of the study subjects and found that 21 (21 %) were having the hypertension, both alcoholic and smoker 15 (15%), diabetes mellitus 12(12%), alcoholic 10(10%), smoker 7(7%) explains the risk factors of study subjects.

We have assessed the co morbidities of the study subjects are found that 20(20%) were having hypertension, 11(11%) having diabetes mellitus, 11(11%) having both diabetes mellitus and hypertension, 3(3%) having diabetes mellitus, hypertension & thyroid, 2(2%) have both thyroid & bronchitis, subjects were affected the hypertension have higher chances of OA knee explains the risk factors of study subjects. Out of 100 subjects 53 (53%) subjects were having pain on Bilateral knee OA, while 26 (26%) subjects having pain on right knee OA and 21 (21%) subjects having pain on left knee OA. gives complete description about distribution based on affected knee .Out of 100 subjects 59 (59%) were grade II knee OA, in the 34 subjects were given Aceclofenac + paracetamol and 25 subjects were given piroxicam followed by 34

(34%) were grade III knee OA, in the 15 subjects were given Aceclofenac + paracetamol and 19 subjects were piroxicam, in that 7 (7%) subjects were grade IV knee OA, in the 1 subject were Aceclofenac + paracetamol and 6 subjects were piroxicam for the knee OA. Gives complete information of grades.

Assessment of VAS SCORE for the GROUP A subjects before drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain (1-3) is 0, moderate pain is (4-6) is 30(60%) and severe pain (7-10) is 20(40%), Explains Assessment of VAS SCORE for Group- A subjects before drug therapy. Assessment of VAS SCORE for the GROUP A subjects first follow up drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain (1-3) is 11(22%), moderate pain is (4-6) is 33(66%) and severe pain (7-10) is 6(12%), Assessment of VAS SCORE for the GROUP A subjects second follow up drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain (1-3) is 7(15%), moderate pain is (4-6) is 39(83%) and severe pain (7-10) is 1(2%),

Assessment of VAS SCORE for the GROUP B subjects before drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain (1-3) is 0, moderate pain is (4-6) is 16(32%) and severe pain (7-10) is 34(68%), Assessment of VAS SCORE for the GROUP B subjects first follow up drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain (1-3) is 8(16%), moderate pain is (4-6) is 29(58%) and severe pain (7-10) is 13(26%), Assessment of VAS SCORE for the GROUP B subjects Second follow up drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain (1-3) is 5(11%), moderate pain is (4-6) is 26(55%) and severe pain (7-10) is 7(15%).

Assessment of WOMAC SCALE for the GROUP A subjects before drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain is 1(2%), moderate pain is 32(64%) ,severe pain is 15(30%)and extreme pain 2(4%) , Assessment of WOMAC SCALE for the GROUP A subjects first follow up drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain is 6(12%), moderate pain is 37(74%) ,severe pain is 7(14%)and extreme pain 0. Assessment of WOMAC SCALE for the GROUP A subjects second follow up drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain is 3(8%), moderate pain is 35(70%), severe pain is 9(22%) and extreme pain 0.

Assessment of WOMAC SCALE for the GROUP B subjects before drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain is 1(2%), moderate pain is 25(50%) ,severe pain is 23(46%)and extreme pain 1(2%), Assessment of WOMAC SCALE for the GROUP B subjects first drug follow up drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain is 1(2%), moderate pain is 31(62%) ,severe pain is 17(34%) and extreme pain 1(2%), Assessment of WOMAC SCALE for the GROUP B subjects

second drug follow up drug therapy categorise pain, whereas mild pain is 1(2%), moderate pain is 25(50%), severe pain is 13(27%) and extreme pain 0. For the VAS SCORE P value for Group A is 0.003 & P value for Group B is 0.06, among Group A & Group B, Group A is significant For the WOMAC SCALE P value for Group A is 0.0016 & P value for Group B is 0.25, among Group A & Group B, Group A is significant

VAS SCORE		GROUP A		GROUP B	
		NO OF SUBJECTS	TOTAL NO OF SUBJECTS	NO OF SUBJECTS	TOTAL NO OF SUBJECTS
BASELINE			50		50
	Mild Pain (1-3)	0		0	
	Moderate Pain (4-6)	30		16	
	Severe Pain (7-10)	20		34	
FOLLOW UP I			50		50
	Mild Pain (1-3)	11		8	
	Moderate Pain (4-6)	33		29	
	Severe Pain (7-10)	6		13	
FOLLOW UP II			47		38
	Mild Pain (1-3)	7		5	
	Moderate Pain (4-6)	39		26	
	Severe Pain (7-10)	1		7	

Table: 1 Distribution Of Vas Score For Group A & Group B Subjects' Base Line, Follow Up I & II Drug Therapy:

WOMAC SCALE		GROUP A		GROUP B	
		NO OF SUBJECTS	TOTAL NO OF SUBJECTS	NO OF SUBJECTS	TOTAL NO OF SUBJECTS
BASELINE	Mild Pain	1	50	1	50
	Moderate Pain	32		25	
	Severe Pain	15		23	
	Extreme	2		1	
FOLLOW UP I	Mild Pain	6	50	1	50
	Moderate Pain	37		31	
	Severe Pain	7		17	
	Extreme	0		1	
FOLLOW UP II	Mild Pain	3	47	1	39
	Moderate Pain	35		25	
	Severe Pain	9		13	
	Extreme	0		0	

Table: 2 Distributions Of Womac Scale For Group A & Group B Subjects' Base Line, Follow Up I & II Drug Therapy:

VAS	Aceclofenac + Paracetamol (Group-A)		Piroxicam (Group-B)	
	Before	After	Before	After
MEAN	6.12	4.7	6.88	5.4
S. D±	1.62	1.61	1.41	1.58
<i>P-Value</i>	0.003 **		0.06*	
P-Value: * Significant, ** Very Significant.				
WOMAC				
MEAN	2.38	2.0	2.48	2.36
S. D±	0.64	0.52	0.52	0.52
<i>P value</i>	0.0016**		0.25	
P-Value: * Significant, ** Very Significant, > 0.25 Not Significant				

Table: 3 Interpretations Of Comparison Of Vas Scale & Womac Score

VAS	P VALUE
Aceclofenac+ Paracetamol	0.0017**
Piroxicam	
P-Value: ** Very Significant	
WOMAC	P VALUE
Aceclofenac+ Paracetamol	0.0036**
Piroxicam	
P-Value: ** Very Significant	

Table: 4 Interpretations Of Comparison Of P Value For Vas Scale & Womac Score

Out of 100 subjects, 8 experienced ADRs with 3 cases reported in Group-A and 5 cases reported in Group-B. In Group-A the reported adverse effects included constipation, headache, and allergic reaction, while dizziness and gastrointestinal irritation were not observed. Subjects in the Group B reported a higher overall number of ADRs, specially experiencing one case of each of constipation, dizziness, headache, allergic reaction, and GI irritation. The group-B had greater incidence of adverse drug reactions compared to Group-A.

DISCUSSION:

This study suggested that Aceclofenac + Paracetamol has shown benefit for osteoarthritis subjects than Piroxicam. In our study by using students T test between two groups p-value for VAS scale for group A is 0.003 and for group-B is 0.06 and p-value for WOMAC scale for group-A is 0.0016 and for group-

B is 0.25. Which shows that strong presumption i.e. p-value <0.05.

OA is more common in women than men but the prevalence increases, we observed the number of subjects based on gender, male is 41 and female is 59. The same will be reported by *Hawker, G. A., and Stewart*. We observed and categorised the subjects according to their age groups the average age off total study population is 55 years. We observed the number of subjects based on gender, male is 41 and female is 59. The same will be reported by *David T. Felson, Md.*

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